

IMPROVING PHYSICAL FITNESS OF CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE BASED ON INCREASING PHYSICAL ACTIVIT

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Abstract: The article describes the process of physical education, which provides for the creation of basic physical fitness of schoolchildren in secondary schools, the formation of a fund of movement skills, and the comprehensive development of a person.

Keywords: Physical training, movement activity, research methods, pedagogical observations, primary school age.

Improving the quality of education is one of the urgent problems of the science of pedagogy, and solving this problem aimed at modernizing the content of education, optimizing pedagogical technologies in the organization of the educational process is an urgent task.

The process of physical education in general education schools provides the foundation of the basic physical fitness of schoolchildren, the formation of a fund of movement skills, and the comprehensive development of the individual.

It is noted that primary school age is the most favorable period for purposefully influencing children's physical development and mobility.

The education system for children of primary school age is of particular importance. The period of education of junior high school students is a decisive stage in the life of a child, in which new educational conditions, a high total educational load, adaptation to a new routine, the novelty and complexity of the studied material, to learning the need following the teacher's assignments and instructions places high demands on their bodies. Physical training and fitness activities are an effective means of eliminating accumulated fatigue.

Starting the research, we started from the assumption that it is possible to significantly increase the level of physical fitness of children of this age group based on increasing physical activity.

During the day, physical activity is large and distributed in waves. In children of primary school age (7-8 years old), natural motor activity gives three maximum levels: one is from 7 to 8 in the morning, and the other is from 15 to 17 at the end of training when walking in the air. Dynamic studies of natural motor activity show that the number of movements also varies depending on the day of the week, increases from Monday to Thursday, decreases on Saturday and slightly increases on Sunday.

The manifestation of motor activity also depends on the gender of children and adolescents. Many studies show that girls have a much lower need for exercise, and their daily activity is 20-30% lower than that of men in almost all age groups.

Compared to boys, girls have much less daily physical activity due to the reduction in the number of unorganized muscle movements. The first shows independent movement activity, performing 44% of the total number of movements due to forced exercises, and 56% due to organized forms.

In physical education classes, boys show approximately 57-60% of movements in the form of unorganized movements and only 40% in various types of organized movements. There are also differences in the nature of actions.

In healthy, properly developing and well-functioning schoolchildren, the number of daily activities changes significantly with the return. Initially, until the age of 10, the number of muscle movements increases year by year, and from the age of 11, it gradually decreases in waves.

Motor activity depends on the individual characteristics of the genetic code and the social conditions of students. It has been proven that the typological characteristics of the nervous system play an important role in the formation of individual characteristics of the manifestation of various forms of movement. According to N. T. Lebedeva, among primary school students, 52% are balanced, 28% are excited, and 20% are inert children. The movement activity of children in all three groups is not the same: it is more in excitable children, less in inert children than in children with balanced nervous processes. The individuality of motor behavior is also reflected in the distribution of ups and downs in activity during the day.

Shunday qilib, barcha maktab o'quvchilarida kuniga bir necha marta motor faolligining ko'tarilishi saqlanib qoladi, ammo ularning kattaligi har doim ham bir xil emas. Motor faoliyatining namoyon bo'lishida maktab o'quvchilarining yashash sharoitlari muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bola tanasining motor qobiliyatlari uchun maktab o'quvchilari yashaydigan, o'qiydigan va bo'sh vaqtlarini o'tkazadigan binolarning o'lchamlari muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maktab o'quvchilarining yashash joyining maktabdan uzoqligi ham umumiy kundalik jismoniy faoliyatga ta'sir qiladi.

Children who have to walk long distances to school every day without the use of transportation receive a higher dose of traffic than children who live close to school. In this regard, rural children have advantages over their urban peers.

Studying the results of the introduction of systematically organized physical education lessons into the daily lifestyle of schoolchildren shows that optimizing the movement activity of students has a positive effect on their mental activity.

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